

Research

Study on Opium Addiction and Its Problems During Implementing Anesthesia

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Accepted: 20 December 2019; Online: 24 December 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592547>

Abstract: *Opium is a highly addictive non-synthetic narcotic that is extracted from the poppy plant. The opium poppy is a critical source for many drugs, including morphine, codeine, and heroin. Opium abuse creates diseases that scientists consider as part of psychiatric disorders. So opium abusers have several significant challenges during the anesthesia for surgical operations. The aim of this study is twofold: first, review of the status of problems of opium abusers in anesthesia, and second, review the clinical management problems of patients with opium abusers during anesthesia, based on the evidence in this field. During the peri-operative, these medical issues discuss the new clinical outcomes for these patients and demonstrate some of the main problems facing physicians.*

Keywords: *Anesthesia, Abuse, Drug, Opium*

1. Introduction

Opium is one of the oldest substances in the world to be abused. It was referred to many years ago as an anesthetic drug, including the Shahnameh and Avicenna quotations on opioids (A Dabbagh, Rajaei, and Golzari 2014; Zarghami 2015). Furthermore, opioid derivatives and their pharmaceutical products are used in advanced medical methods, and drug addiction patients pose a unique challenge for the medical team during a procedure (Wall and Did 2007; Sleigh 2010; Zarghami 2015).

Opioids are usually used for acute and chronic pain. The long term use of these medications, in particular in chronic pain situations, can, however, lead to the development of heroin addiction, which can lead to cross-tolerance between LA and opioids (Razavi et al. 2019). Chronic opium abuse causes several cellular changes in pain receptors. These changes make the opium abuser

more resistant to both opioid analgesics and non-opioid analgesics, for instance, local anesthetics (Razavi et al. 2019). It has been observed in clinical settings that regional anesthesia duration is shorter in opium dependent individuals; as a result, they are in a greater need for the intravenous administration of analgesic medications and sedatives. Various causes have been mentioned for the influence of opium in addicts in terms of duration, including the cross-tolerance between local anesthesia and opioids.

The study is structured as follows: section two presents the Methodology of research, section three reviews the status of the problem of patient with opium abuse in anesthesiology and its clinical management or its problems when implementing anesthesia Section four concludes the opium abusers problems in anesthesiology, and it is the clinical management of problem of patients with opium abuse.

2. Methods

A comprehensive literature review develops a conceptual framework for opium addiction and its anesthetics problems. The present study is evidence-based descriptive. At first, the paper has put attention at preliminary studies related to issues of patients with opium abuse in anesthesiology. Then it focuses on opium users' anesthetic problems during operation.

2.1 Research Strategy and Data analysis

The data has been thoroughly searched using keywords such as Opium, Anesthesia, and Anesthesiology from several renowned sources, including Google Scholars, a science site, science direct, and Springer. The data collection and analysis for this paper has been done during October 2019. Literature reviews are a significant part of this study. It provides for the development and evaluation of previous research and thus creating a safe context for knowledge growth. In this study, the data is analyzed from different perspectives of Anesthesiology for the operation of Opium users when implementing anesthesia and at the time of surgery.

3. Status of problems of the patient with opium abuse in anesthesiology

This research discusses the causes of various cellular adjustments in pain perception through persistent opium abuse. First, we think about changes depending on mechanisms, and then we identify two pain control anatomical sources: heart, spinal cord, and peripheral nerves. While these studies have been categorized in several subclasses, they have often overlapped.

a. Rol of Genetic in Pain management of the patient with Opium Abuse

Some genes desensitize people to opium abuse; these genes should depend on further studies; in the care of opium abusers, we ought to believe in "genetic predisposition." Also, manipulating these genes could be a potential, but very effective method for changing the behavioral patterns of opium abusers. Possibly, soon, we could at least detect these genes to treat opium abusers undergoing anesthesia in a more appropriate manner or even, we will be able to produce much more appropriate pharmacologic agents for managing opium abusers undergoing anesthesia (Briand and Blendy 2010; Shippenberg and Zapata 2007; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).

b. Receptor changes in Pain Management of the patient with Opium Abuse

Patients with opium abuse experience some considerable changes in neural receptors; for these reasons, the receptors of opium change their response from a normal response to pain to an abnormal response. These changes, are resulting from the reaction of receptors to repeated opium exposure, i.e., opium attachment to the receptor does not elicit the normal intracellular RNA production process; which would result in synthesis of different and abnormal proteins; the resulting change in protein synthesis causes different clinical responses like pain intolerance, hyperalgesia, allodynia or other clinical phenomena seen in these patients which are primarily due to modifications in receptor response; these mechanisms are under further research and contribute an active field of studies which could create new horizons not only for opium abusers but also for other chronic pain patients and include: up-regulation of substance P, up-regulation of Calcium Gene Related Peptide (CGRP), changes in inhibition of Nitric Oxide, modifications in inhibitors of cyclooxygenase, abnormal inhibition of Protein kinase C, adjustments in antagonistic response of NMDA (N-methyl-D-aspartate) receptor, changes in antagonism of alpha-amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4 isoxazolepropionic acid (AMPA) receptor, antagonism of cholecystinin (CCK), changes in L-type Calcium channel response (L-type Ca channel could be blocked with amlodipine to overcome some effects of opium tolerance) (King et al. 2005; Angst and Clark 2006; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).

3.1 Rol of the immune system for Pain Management of the patient with Opium Abuse

Patient with repeated opium exposure shows some considerable immunological changes. These immunological changes can induce pain intolerance in inpatient. Some primary immunologic responses in opium abusers include the increased ratio of pro-inflammatory interleukins compared to anti-inflammatory interleukins, expression of NK-1 receptor in the dorsal horn of the spine,

facilitating pain conduction, the role of Toll-like receptors especially TLR-5 in chronic pain and its modulation and other components of both innate and adaptive immunologic system. These changes will result in partial ineffectiveness of anesthetic agents, needing extra regular anesthetic drugs, or an inability to control stress response, which its control is an essential goal in anesthesia care during the preoperative period (Vera Portocarrero et al. 2007; Z. Xu et al. 2015; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016). There are three anatomical parts for pain control of patient with Opium Abuse: **Brain, Spinal Cord and Peripheral Nerves**. We discuss the Brain and Spinal Cord as following:

- a. Brain:** Due to some changes in brain response to neurotransmitters, cells, signal processing, and other change in brain neural circuits, which sometimes lead to partially permanent trophic changes resulting in considerable clinical challenges. These changes create an abnormal pattern of signal transmission in different parts of the brain, including the thalamus, locus coeruleus, and other nuclei. For example; changes in cholecystikinin level in the rostral ventromedial medulla in repeated exposure to opioids results in up regulation of CCK; increased CCK will activate facilitation of descending pain pathways, which is relayed via the dorsolateral funiculus, leading to hyperalgesia (King et al. 2005; Ossipov et al. 2005; Karbasy and Derakhshan 2014; Ossipov et al. 2004; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016), the neurons located in locus coeruleus have specific relation with mu receptor and they are coupled with K channels; while, increased excitatory neurotransmission through nucleus para gigantocellular could be among the mechanisms that make opium tolerance more severe (Han et al. 2006; King et al. 2005; Ossipov et al. 2004; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016), opium by itself could induce brain apoptosis which may be associated with defects in some parts of brain function (Asiabanha et al. 2011) neuroplastic, and neurotrophic changes are those cellular level changes due to repeated opium exposure that show themselves as a different response to opium and opioid agents; these changes are not as much severe as apoptosis; however, they create abnormal patterns of brain function and are so-called “pronociceptive changes”(Chu, Angst, and Clark 2015; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).
- b. Spinal Cord:** local spinal neuronal circuits and Spinal Cord ascending and descending pathways, could be classified into the following methods: pain elicited through descending facilitation which is the primary source of spinal cord obtained shock in opium abusers (Lee et al. 2015), up-regulation of spinal dynorphin which could also have interactions with bradykinin receptors; the final result would be aggravated hyperalgesia with neuroexcitatory effect and the resulting pronociceptive pain in the spinal cord (J. Xu et al. 2015), excitatory neurotransmitters

which their release induces severe pain through spinal cord mechanisms, the role of mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAP kinase) family, especially the role of TGF- β activated kinase 1 in producing pain through the spinal cord (J. Xu et al. 2015).

3.2 Opium Users Anesthetic Problems During Operation

Opium abusers encounters very remarkable problems which are essential for anesthetist and surgeon as tow responsible individuals for saving survival the patient has abused the opium, at first, he will need increased anesthetic drugs to tolerate surgery; in fact, the studies related to these patients have demonstrated some clinical findings that confirm the findings in animal studies or other fundamental researches: chronic opium abuse is a significant etiology for receptor changes regarding sensation and pain perception through different mechanisms explained in previous paragraphs.

These changes make the opium abusers more resistant to both opioid analgesics and non-opioid analgesics (like local anesthetics); a clinical finding in concordance with other studies demonstrating the effects of chronic opium abuse on the cellular mechanisms of pain sensation and the bizarre, extensive changes in the pain perception structures of opium abusers (A Dabbagh et al. 2007; Dahi- Taleghani et al. 2014; A Dabbagh et al. 2011).

The problem with these patients during the intraoperative period is that excessive opioid use results in an increased chance for postoperative apnea and also, delayed emergence from anesthesia after the termination of surgery. However, several other anesthetic drugs have been used successfully in opium abusers with good results; including ketamine, dexmedetomidine, and clonidine to replace the commonly used analgesic agents, i.e., opioid derivative (Dahi- Taleghani et al. 2014):

- **Dexmedetomidine:** among the above, dexmedetomidine could be promising with both opium sparing effects and CNS protecting mechanisms. Dexmedetomidine decreases the needed analgesic requirements in the perioperative period and also has the property to manage opium abusers during the perioperative period, primarily the opioid-induced hyperalgesia phenomenon; studies have demonstrated that dexmedetomidine could be used for the treatment of opium withdrawal syndrome (Omami et al. 2015).

- Clonidine has similar chemical properties with dexmedetomidine while it is not precisely the same; however, clonidine and lofexidine, both alpha 2 agonists, could be used for the treatment of opium withdrawal in opium abusers.

- Ketamine could be used in opium abusers with fewer respiratory depression events leading to opioid-sparing results; however, pain control with ketamine may be associated with several delirious states that should elicit cautious when using this agent; the clinical solution is to use ketamine as low dose and infusion to prevent the untoward effects as much as possible and to have appropriate analgesic properties (Dahi- Taleghani et al. 2014; Garai et al. 2013; Vosoughin, Mohammadi, and Dabbagh 2012).
- Paracetamol has an efficacious profile for these patients acting through non-opioid analgesic mechanisms.

In opium abusers, there is an alternative approach, and this alternative approach is to use regional anesthesia; including spinal, epidural and other methods of regional anesthesia; however, the growing bulk of evidence demonstrates that opium abusers have cross-tolerance to local anesthetics, mainly including lidocaine and bupivacaine; although, the mechanism for tolerance is similar between these agents and possibly other forms of local anesthetics are identical regarding the tolerance phenomenon; this clinical and pharmacological phenomenon presents clinically as shortened duration of action (A Dabbagh et al. 2007; Karbasy and Derakhshan 2014; Dahi-Taleghani et al. 2014).

This cross-tolerance is an authentic problem, encountered both clinically and proved in necessary studies; the underlying mechanism stands based on the plastic neuronal changes in the spinal cord, which create a tolerance to both opioids and local anesthetics (A Dabbagh et al. 2007; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).

Several adjuvant drugs have been used with relatively successful results leading to improved regional anesthesia duration and increased analgesic properties; some studies focus on adjuvant drugs to local anesthetics to improve their length of analgesia in opium abusers to overcome the rescue analgesia properties (Abdollahpour et al. 2015; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016): first of all, opioids combined with local anesthetics in regional anesthesia improve the analgesic potency and decrease the rescue analgesic requirements, the safety profiles for most of these drugs are well established; however, sometimes we need to be more cautious to consider their safety profile, other pharmaceuticals, including magnesium sulfate, neostigmine, dexmedetomidine, paracetamol, midazolam, and others agents have been used for regional anesthesia with acceptable levels of success (Garai et al. 2013; Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).

Final problem with opium is that it may be “significant allergen” and may create some forms of anaphylaxis in operating room; the mechanism of allergy is mainly anaphylaxis, and other types of immune reaction are not much common; at times, impaired hemodynamics may ensue; even when opium is used as an oral agent and could cause hypotension (Ali Dabbagh and Rajaei 2016).

4. Conclusions

Opium abuse remains a significant challenge for our clinics, and a great deal more needs to be done to improve our clinical results; while during the preoperative process there are several severe problems for patients abusing opium, some promising points still exist that help us look to the future with positive and optimistic inspiration as followings:

1. Newly established medications, such as dexmedetomidine, could boost the potential anesthesia, with an acceptable level of patient satisfaction, of all patients, including opioid abusers, to reduce the chances of unpleasant complications (like respiratory depression and post-operative delirium).
2. Among opioid addicts with opium sparing effects, other older drugs such as clonidine, magnesium, and ketamine had relatively high outcomes.
3. Local anesthesia procedures can have improved effectiveness using adjuvant drugs.

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